

Supplementary material for Integrated multi-scale workflow for assessing land use and land cover change: Evidence from Cairo

Table A. Description of land use and land cover (LULC) classes identified in the study area.

Source: The authors

Land Cover Type	Description
Water	All water bodies, including the Nile River, canals, lakes, ponds, and reservoirs. This class represents natural and artificial open water features within the study area.
Vegetation	Areas dominated by natural or managed vegetation, including agricultural lands, urban green spaces, parks, gardens, and street trees.
Built-up Area	Constructed and impervious surfaces, including residential, commercial, industrial, service areas, roads, bridges, quarries, and cemeteries.
Bare Land	Land with little to no vegetation cover, including desert, exposed soil, sand, vacant land, and undeveloped open spaces.

Table B. Initial distribution of reference (ground-truth) samples by land-use and land-cover class for 2014 and 2024 before class down-sampling, illustrating the degree of class imbalance in the training data. Source: The authors

Class	Samples by class 2014	Samples by class 2024
Water	720	1426
Vegetation	3006	3896

Built up	17656	61100
Bare land	253168	274518

Table C. Accuracy assessment results for LULC classification for (2014 and 2024) Source: The authors

Year	Classified	Water	Vegetation	Built-up	Bare land	Producer's
2014	Water	209	1	0	1	99.1
	Vegetation	0	434	5	0	98.9
	Built-up	0	3	448	3	98.7
	Bare land	0	0	6	428	98.6
	User's Accuracy	100	99.1	98.7	99.3	
	Overall Accuracy					98.76
	Kappa					0.983
2024	Water	406	2	0	0	99.5
	Vegetation	1	839	16	3	97.7
	Built-up	0	16	842	4	97.7
	Bare land	0	0	7	853	99.2
	User's Accuracy	99.8	97.9	97.3	99.5	
	Overall Accuracy					98.36
	Kappa					0.978

Table D. Quantitative comparison of land use/land cover (LULC) classes in 2014 and 2024

LULC Class	Area 2014 (km²)	Percentage 2014 (%)	Area 2024 (km²)	Percentage 2024 (%)	Percentage Change (%)
Water	14.29	1.77	13.59	1.68	-4.90
Vegetation	37.63	4.66	25.06	3.10	-33.40
Built-up	331.09	40.97	436.69	54.03	+31.89
Bare land	425.18	52.61	332.85	41.18	-21.71

Table E. Land use and land cover (LULC) transition matrix showing area (km²) and percentage distribution of land cover conversions between 2014 and 2024. Source: The authors

From LULC class	To LULC class	Area (km²)	Percentage (%)
Bare land	Bare land	309.33	38.27
Bare land	Built-up	113.40	14.03
Bare land	Vegetation	2.33	0.29
Bare land	Water	0.12	0.01
Built-up	Built-up	304.64	37.69
Built-up	Bare land	21.78	2.70
Built-up	Vegetation	4.43	0.55

Built-up	Water	0.24	0.03
Vegetation	Built-up	18.39	2.28
Vegetation	Bare land	1.68	0.21
Vegetation	Vegetation	17.30	2.14
Vegetation	Water	0.26	0.03
Water	Water	12.98	1.61
Water	Vegetation	1.00	0.12
Water	Built-up	0.25	0.03
Water	Bare land	0.06	0.01
